

Urban Renewal and Displacement: Implications for Crime

A Study of Port Harcourt, Rivers State, Nigeria

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Abstract:- This paper examined the implications of urban renewal and displacement for crime in Port Harcourt. This paper also looked at the socio-economic effects of massive urban renewal on the dwellers of Port Harcourt and the measures that can be put in place to prevent the hardship occasioned by urban renewal in Port Harcourt. This study was anchored on social ecological, and hybrids integrated theories approaches. The design of the study was a descriptive survey. This study uses secondary data. Content analysis was utilized to analyze the data to achieve the objectives of the study. The study shows that internal displacement, acute poverty, homelessness, family breakdown, severe unemployment, depression, economic recession, incomplete schooling and social isolation are some of the socio-economic impacts of urban renewal in Port Harcourt. Displacements caused by urban renewal have resulted to commercial sex, robbery, cultism and political thuggery during elections, oil bunkering, kidnapping, armed robbery, theft and stealing. Also, the study revealed that planning, public hearing, revocation of rights of occupancy, displacement and relocation are measures that can be put in place to prevent the hardship occasioned by urban renewal in Port Harcourt. Consequently, the study recommends that Nigerian Government should make urban renewal exercise one that charges residents of communities likely to be affected, takes them away, pays required compensation, or if necessary relocates them before the demolition action begins.

Keyword:- Urban Renewal, Displacement, Implications, Crime.

I. INTRODUCTION

Every year, the global urban population grows by about 70 million, equivalent to seven megacities (Jimoh, Omole, and Omosulu 2013). These must be accommodated, fed and used according to the traffic capacity of these urban centers, so they must be cared for. Most of these are located in developing countries and therefore pose a number of logistical challenges for urban planning. According to (Norwegian Refugee Council (NRC) 2015), the global urban population grows by 5 million. African nations have better charge of urbanization and are much less urbanized in comparison to nations within aside the advanced world. Among these, however, sub-Saharan Africa turned into suggested to have the biggest percentage of urban slum

dwellers 71%. It is predicted that among 28% of urban increase in growing nations is informal, generally inhabited via way of means of low-profits humans (Aluko & Amidu, 2006). Nigeria is not any exception to this venture which makes this have a look at even extra pertinent. This is unconnected with an excessive charge of populace influx from rural to urban regions, therefore, inflicting decline of the financial system and fortune of urban regions in part due to the fact there aren't any commercial and different monetary expansions to suit the influx (Adekola, Allen, & Tinuola, 2017; Adekola 2016).

Today, 50 percent of Nigerians stay in urban regions, which are predicted to grow to over sixty-five according to cent in 2050 (PRB, 2015). Huang (2008) cited that the nice technique to accomplishing sustainable city improvement and retarding the charge of city decay is enough to take care of current towns which additionally includes city renewal. Urban renewal has also been considered as a strategy for eliminating undesirable individuals and creating additional job opportunities (Zielenbach & Levin, 2000), reaching sustainable provision of utilities (Van der Brugge & de Graaf, 2010), enhancing the dwelling environment (Kara, 2011), growing new and green financial activities (McDonald, Malys, & Meliene, 2009), constructing sustainable groups and enhancing socio-financial integration in city areas (Fadare & Oduwaye, 2009; Dimuna & Omatsone, 2010). Therefore, the different urban renewal strategies should be seen as veritable planning tools for improving and sustaining the viability of urban neighbourhoods, and thus promoting sustainable development.

Urban renewal is not a burn-and-burn process, anyway a complete and all encompassing way to deal with reestablishing the aging urban fabric through restoration, recovery and landmark safeguarding. Notwithstanding, in Africa, and in Federal Republic of Nigeria specifically, recovery is by all accounts doing extra damage than great. Especially inside the principal months when the execution. In the same way, the incidental outcomes next to constrained relocation, social bending or dislodging, inward uprooting and differed others because of the recovery of the town are financially affecting the occupants of Port Harcourt. Removal related changes incorporate third-layered impoverishment, absence of homes, networks, efficient land, monetary benefit abundance, livelihoods, local area shared assets, and social destinations. Fairness for a huge number of people round the world who are uprooted by improvement cannot be ensured,

the ramifications they face is likewise moderately critical. While, individuals dislodged from their homes by tremors or fights are seen well by the media or worldwide guide associations, the survivors of removal incited improvement ordinarily don't win that compassion. In spite of the way that the pessimistic effects of natural cycle relocation can be even pretty much as serious as those carefully prepared by individuals dislodged by various powers (Robinson, 2003). Following the removals brought about by urban renewal in Port Harcourt, tenants became vulnerable, disjoined of family ties, genuine joblessness, melancholy, inadequate tutoring and social separation. Therefore, many resort to crime as a means of survival. This research will be guided by the following questions:

- i. Is there any relationship between the urban renewal programme displacement and crime in Port Harcourt?
- ii. What are the socio-economic effects of the massive urban renewal programme on the dwellers of Port Harcourt?
- iii. Had there been measures put in place by government to mitigate the hardship occasioned by the urban renewal in Port Harcourt?

A. Objectives of the Study

The objectives of this study are to:

- Examine the relationship between the urban renewal programme, displacement and crime in Port Harcourt.
- Find out the socio-economic effects of the massive urban renewal programme on the dwellers of Port Harcourt.
- Find out if there were measures put in place by government to mitigate the hardship occasioned by the urban renewal programme in Port Harcourt.

B. Clarification of Concepts

The concepts of urban renewal, displacement and crime are defined for better understanding and appreciation of this paper.

Urban Renewal: Lee (2008) characterizes it as a strategy that comprises of freedom of ghetto or scourge districts, urban renewal of events, urban renewal, developing restoration, upkeep and protection to improve urban material and meet a couple of financial and social targets. Urban renewal will build the social standing and capital abundance of a spot (Nwanna 2012; Lee 2008). It also lessens wrongdoing charge inside the region, decorates the environmental factors, eases back rural spread, and diminishes wantonness for a higher arranged metropolitan (PLB, 2000). Urban renewal has been characterized as a gadget for hindering or completing urban out of date quality, halting urban rot, clearing cursed locales and updating disintegrated structures, real environmental elements, and infrastructure (Okeke, 2004; George, 2006).

Displacement: Displacement is the elimination of something from its normal vicinity or function through something which then occupies that vicinity or function.

Cermea, (2000) argues that displacement encompasses all forms of disturbance resulting from the forced uprooting of people from their physical, economic, social, cultural and psychological location. All of these are processes of

involuntary displacement that affect people's livelihoods or put them at risk of annihilation.

Crime: Crime is like various standards in the social sciences, which generally do not have a unified definition. A crime is defined as a wrongdoing that rises above the private circle and generally enter the public and disregards any standard or prohibitory law to which material punishments or approvals apply which are joined and require the intercession of a public power. For the criminal offense to be characterized accordingly, it should be known and managed by an authoritative or law requirement office. According to Adebayo (2013), the offense is equally visible as a breach of the agreed norms of having a good reputation, using all members of society and the other members of society sanctioning the guilty of rape.

C. Area of Study

Port Harcourt the capital of Rivers State is found inside the Niger Delta Region of African country with very 5 ethnic groups or identities. The town is the modern operational hub of the state and has throughout the years seen an inflow of transients from the rural networks any place farmland are obliterated as a consequences of oil investigation and double-dealing by global oil enterprises. Such regions embrace Ogoni, Etche, Abua and Ikwerre among different. Port Harcourt could be a significant modern place since it includes a sizable measure of worldwide firms in basically the same manner as other modern worries, essentially rough industry. Starting at 2016, Port Harcourt metropolitan has partner measurable populace of 1,865,000, that was considered to have adult from the 2006 authority evaluation populace figure of 1,382,592 occupants (NPC, 2006).

D. Theoretical Foundation

Many research works have demonstrated the clarifications for restoration to be different, depending on the needs of the occupants and accordingly the engineers. There are two significant groups of standards to explain this peculiarity: social-ecological and hybrids integrated theories.

E. Social Ecological Theory

Social ecological theory was proposed by Bronfenbrenner, U (1992). He clarified the theory as the investigation of the social and movement outcomes of the association among humans and their environmental factors. It explicitly investigates the causes and results of cycles of isolation the rise through decision of natural totally separation on key aspects respect populace organization and land use. It researches anyway openness to various conditions (region and spot based differential social design and exercises) impacts human turn of events and activity. Social ecological theory centers around the job of the climate inside the advancement of individuals' differential affinity to connect in wrongdoing and their differential openness to settings contributory to commitment in demonstrations of wrongdoing this hypothesis focuses on investigating and clarifying wrongdoing among the metropolitan climate. In elective words, this theory exudes from the investigation of a few rustic urban regions.

F. *Hybrids Integrated Theory*

Hybrid theorists such as Damarius (1984), Hamnett (1984), and Cough (1990), in their own illustrative papers on urban renewal, scrutinized the over-conclusion of urban renewal studies by urban environmentalists and neo-Marxists, and required its incorporation in the learning. For instance, Hamnett (1984), in the wake of contrasting different theories of urban renewal, outstandingly Smith's (1979), to abiding theory, placed that there are five principle illustrative variables for metropolitan recovery. Cases, and they are positioned by significance: (I) the effect of expanding city size alongside changes in the compromise between size inclination and availability, (ii) changes in the segment and family design of the populace, (iii) changes in way of life and inclinations, (iv) changes in relative expansion in lodging and speculation costs; and (v) changes in the work base and word related construction of explicit urban communities. Hamnett (1984) demanded that all sociologists, geographers and other social researchers engaged with metropolitan advancement should concentrate on the peculiarity by responding to the inquiry 'Why, when and where did metropolitan recovery happen?' This will assist with tackling the issue of metropolitan relocation looked by occupants any place this has happened, rather than zeroing in on minor issues that benefit neither the government running the activity nor the inhabitants impacted.

II. METHODOLOGY

The design of the study was a descriptive survey. This study uses secondary data. The secondary data were generated from journals, articles and textbooks. Content analysis was utilized to analyze the data to achieve the objectives of the study.

A. *Situational Analysis*

This study seeks to examine the relationship between urban renewal, displacement and crime in Port Harcourt. It also seeks to expose the socioeconomic effects of massive urban renewal on the dwellers of Port Harcourt and to find out if there were measures put in place by government to mitigate the hardship occasioned by the urban renewal programme in Port Harcourt. This paper follows the textual method of data presentation which involves a narrative description of the data gathered in written, paragraph form, and the answers to the research questions are treated in different sections under different sub-headings to achieve thoroughness and enhance clarity.

B. *Relationship between Urban Renewal, Displacement and Crime in Port Harcourt*

The urbanization programme in Port Harcourt has not been went with a comparing supply of satisfactory lodging, essential infrastructure, and conveniences. This has given a vertical push to the improvement of easygoing settlements and a blast in crime. The distinction among people and their stock of work without provision for some other make them, specifically, the youths, idle and thus, are effortlessly used or lured into crimes and violence in addition to getting used as political thugs through elites. Because they're generally younger humans who've fewer obligations for households

and careers, they are fantastically effortlessly mobilized for social and political conflicts.

According to Wosu and Anele (2010) the youths interact themselves in all styles of illegitimate sports for survival. Out of desperation, they were given concerned in smoking and sale of opium. Others are industrial sex, robbery, cultism and political thuggery throughout elections, oil bunkering, kidnapping, armed robbery, robbery and stealing. Cernea (2004) stated that, urban renewal elicits impoverishment dangers on displaced men and women together with landlessness, joblessness, homelessness, marginalization, accelerated morbidity and mortality, meals insecurity, lack of get admission to not unusual place belongings and services, and social disarticulation and this may compel them to enter crook sports so as to triumph over the issues posed on them due to the renewal. In Port Harcourt, urban crimes are growing continuously. The inequalities in earnings distribution, inner migration and issues of urbanization as a result of migration, unfair spatial sharing, relative social deprivation and disintegration within the urban, immediately have an effect on the society and concrete panorama and create appropriate heritage for crime. Although crime is everyday phenomenon it's miles feasible to finish that the burden and strain of crime step by step will increase whilst people are rendered homeless and there supply of earnings destroyed. When the trouble of shelter, which accelerated in an sudden way throughout urban renewal, isn't always handled, then unlawful systems is probably hooked up through the people and that turns into an area to perpetuate crime.

C. *Implications of Urban Renewal and Displacement for Crime in Port Harcourt*

This subsection basically breaks down the effect of urban renewal and crime relocation in Port Harcourt. Assuming that individuals work in unapproved places alongside high-voltage links, seepage waterways, trenches, green regions and other land saved for public use, the specialists may likewise choose to crush them to stringently consent to the city control plan. Instances of such obliteration have large amounts of Port Harcourt. In July 2000, Rainbow Town, Rivers State, home to an expected 1,000,000 individuals, was obliterated with state government help without huge arrangement for the resettlement, restoration, repayment, or migration of uprooted people (Economic and Social Rights Action Center (SERAC), 2009). a metropolitan recharging exertion by the Central Authority to crush some ghettos on the metropolitan side of Port Harcourt. The state government has neither made a substantial association with the resettlement of many dislodged people nor an opportunities for them. Also, Njemanze, a waterfront settlement in Port Harcourt, was obliterated in August 2009 as a component of the urban renewal plan and an expected 13,000 people were displaced; many had no place to stay for a year or more. In 2008 parts of the main streets Bonny Street and Creek Road were demolished, affecting 25,000 people. In addition, all houses along Gambia Lane and Anyama Street were demolished, leaving citizens and shopkeepers homeless or jobless, and the Mile One Diobu Railway Market was demolished in March 2009. The most recent is the Nkpogu

promenade demolition and Oginigba Trans Amadi massacre and Eleme caravan park with the help of the Rivers State Government in August 2021. The government has no alternative arrangement for thousands of displaced persons. These resulted to the followings:

Armed Robbery: Armed robbery in Port Harcourt is not a recent phenomenon. By the dawn of this century, armed robbery has become one of the most serious crimes in Port Harcourt. People are killed daily and their properties took at home, places of work, or on the highways. There have been many incidents of robbery, both those at gunpoint and without guns, which makes it an issue in Port Harcourt. Displacements caused by urban renewal have compounded this problem.

Drug Peddling: Drug dealing is these days a risky hassle which almost all societies, advanced and growing, are grappling with. But at the same time as maximum of the advanced societies can institute measures that as a minimum contained its unfold via peddling and abuse, the identical

cannot be stated of the growing countries. Rivers State isn't always any one of a kind on this regard. Most of these engaged in both illicit drug offers or abuse are the city poor, and a number of the flourishing markets for illicit pills are within side the city slums as in Port Harcourt.

Kidnapping: Kidnapping is one of Port Harcourt's most common crimes against foreigners and at times locals (Ajikobi, 2017). In Rivers State, many youths search for non-existing jobs out of frustration. Rivers state has been reported as being one of the states with the highest level of kidnapping in the country.

Cyber Scam: Cyber scam Belongs to the own circle of relatives of cybercrimes which entails deceit thru using phones, faxes, computers, ICT and different internet-enabled gadgets online, to dupe greedy, careless, untrue and emotionally susceptible individuals of massive sums of cash or valuables (Ojilere & Oraegbunam, 2017). Displacements caused by urban renewal are one of the causes of cybercrime.

Table 1: Crime Rate in Port Harcourt (capital of Rivers State), 2009-2020

S/N	Crime Rate	Extent
1	Level of crime	80.36 Very High
2	Crime increasing in the past 3 years	65.38 High
3	Worries home broken and things stolen	67.86 High
4	Worries being mugged or robbed	65.38 High
5	Worries car were stolen	63.46 High
6	Worries things from the car were stolen	67.86 High
7	Worries attacked	64.29 High
8	Worries being insulted	38.46 High
9	Worries being subject to a physical attack because of your skin colour, ethnic origin, gender or religion	39.29 High
10	Problem people using or dealing drugs	64.29 High
11	Problem property crimes such as vandalism and theft	71.43 High
12	Problem violent crimes such as assault and armed robbery	82.14 High

Source: <https://www.numbeo.com/crime/in/Port-Harcourt-Nigeria>; Ogele (2020).

D. The Socio-Economic Effects of Massive Urban Renewal on the Dwellers of Port Harcourt

Internal displacements, acute poverty, Helplessness, dislocation of own circle of relatives ties, severe unemployment, depression, monetary downturn, incomplete education, and social isolation are a number of the outcomes of urban renewal recognized in Nigeria (Adekola et al. 2017; Adoga 2016; Uwadiogwu 2015; Nwanna 2012; Aluko & Amidu 2006; Jimoh et al. 2013; Kehinde 2003). Though urban renewal brings a brand new existence to an area because it offers a facelift and improves environmental attractiveness, a few citizens, however, generally go through a few losses in diverse degrees. Many landlords lose their houses even as many citizens discover it hard to resettle after renewal. They must relocate somewhere else in the metropolis in which they are able to come up with the money for primarily based totally on their socio-monetary status. For instance, Nwanna (2012) determined that once the urban renewal at Maroko, a former Lagos slum that out of the 41,776 landlords displaced, the handiest 2,933 have been

taken into consideration for relocation. The relaxant have been not able to come up with the money for the excessive charges of edifices that changed their former abodes, main to problems like stress, emotional breakdown, anxiety, depression, mental trauma, etc., being recorded.

The maximum distinguished implication of city renewal in growing nations is a violation of the economic, social, and cultural (ESC) rights of nearby residents. ESC rights typically encompass the proper to work, proper to social security, the proper to housing, meals, schooling, and the proper to fitness and a wholesome environment, all of which can be without problems inspired with the aid of using forceful evictions (Adekola et al, 2018). Cernea (2004) cited that city renewal elicits impoverishment dangers on displaced men and women which include Landlessness, unemployment, homelessness, exclusion, high morbidity and mortality, food insecurity, lack of access to goods and services in unusual places, and social displacement.

Landlessness: Land seizure eliminates the main establishment whereupon productive frameworks of individuals, modern exercises and livelihoods are assembled. This is the essential type of decapitalization and impoverishment of dislodged individuals as they lose both plant and man-made capital. , absence of benefit, property or method of means, whether or not or presently at this point not the impacted people and need to stream to each and every other area (FDRE, 2008).

Joblessness: The danger of losing salaried work is exceptionally high both in urban travel and in country regions for those working in business, administrations or agribusiness. Notwithstanding, the advancement of new positions is troublesome and requires extensive venture. Joblessness or underemployment between resettlements routinely keeps going long after actual resettlement closes. Vagrancy: Losing a place of refuge will in general be the best progress for some resettlements; yet as far as some might be concerned, vagrancy or a deteriorating of their lodging needs stays a tenacious condition. In a more extensive social sense, the shortfall of a homegrown person from a family and the shortfall of a social region from a gathering will generally prompt estrangement and hardship of position. For exiles, the destitute and the "destitute" are inherent by definition.

Food Insecurity: Forced uprooting increases the risk that people will fall into temporary or chronic undernourishment, defined as calorie-protein intake levels below the minimum necessary for normal growth and work.

Increased Morbidity and Mortality: Massive population displacement threatens to thought process serious decreases in wellness levels. Displacement welcomed on prevailing difficulty and mental injury are once in a while seen with the guide of utilizing the outbreak of resettlement-related illnesses, especially parasitic and vector-borne sicknesses, including jungle fever and schistosomiasis. Risky water supply and improvised sewage structures are becoming helpless against scourges and determined loose bowels, diarrhea, and so forth The most weak portions of the segment range, infants, kids and the older are most impacted Loss of admittance to normal labor and products: for individuals, particularly the landless and Goods, the absence of right of admittance to the properties of the spot normal that they had a place with the resettled networks (pastures, lush regions, water bodies, burial grounds). , quarries, and so on) prompts a huge disintegration in pay and job security. When in doubt, misfortunes of local area property are not made up for with state help. The dislodging that requires actual movement no longer hits the uprooted better, yet additionally the occupant populace, the unaffected individuals who are done moving, yet their neighbors, organizations, markets and sources, notwithstanding the getting populace, individuals, taken over by the dislodged and who could subsequently be tortured securely or disadvantageously. (Australian Department of Foreign Affairs and Trade, 2014). The absence of lodging and things because of constrained removals and the evacuating of a current preliminary of lodging creation additionally harbor the risk of inordinate impoverishment for those impacted. While the macroeconomic results of city development are

positive for essentially all metropolitan populaces, the extreme helpless results that arise for a lot more modest association along numerous essential aspects are no less genuine (Abebe, 2010). Metropolitan recovery destroys current methods of creation, upsets informal communities, ruins large numbers of the removed, undermines their social character, and builds the danger of scourges and wellness issues (Robinson, 2003).

E. Control Measures to Urban Renewal in Port Harcourt

The urban renewal measure must not be an unrestrained or warlike invasion or conquest with military might. Port Harcourt must have at least one state-level government agency with other local-level sub-agencies that must be responsible for the coordination, oversight and implementation of urban regeneration projects to ensure a smooth and successful operation. These are the following measures:

Planning: The agency identifies an area or neighborhood **in need of rehabilitation** and draws up a **rehabilitation plan**, which is **analyzed** and approved by **the competent** authorities for **its** implementation.

Sensitization/Consultation of the Citizens or Public Hearing: The public meeting on the proposed redesign program happens at neighborhood level to offer residents/invested individuals the chance to offer their viewpoint and furthermore to perceive the requirement for remodel.

Land Acquisition (Revocation of Rights of Occupancy): Ideally, the impacted land and structures ought to be gained by the public authority (or its office) through private arrangement/concurrences with the proprietors and, in outrageous circumstances where this comes up short, through the activity of the force of a famous area. In this large number of circumstances, the expert administrations of appraisers and land appraisers are required.

Removal and Relocation: Affected families and business are either given financial pay or resettled in elective area or both.

Site Clearance: This includes destroying and evacuation of trash of structures and constructions considered un-valuable by the restoration authority.

Site Improvement and Supporting Facilities/Infrastructure: Provisions of very much developed streets/roads, water supply circulation organization, lighting frameworks, and other social conveniences and administrations follow site freedom.

Disposition of Improved Land: The better land/locales can be arranged through deal, rent or gift to private financial backers or held by the public authority organization.

New Construction/Development: New reestablishment or improvement follows demeanor of the high level land. Be that

as it may, the utilization and improvement should be completely in consonance with a standard designated use and plan acknowledged with the guide of utilizing the legal business venture responsible for the reestablishment project. The new creation may be for private, modern or business depending at the way of thinking and idea of the legal business undertaking that facilitates the venture.

III. CONCLUSION

Urban renewal in Port Harcourt can be likened to the hostile agricultural term 'slash and burn' because the people who benefit suffer the consequences. This is because we found significant associations between urban regeneration in Port Harcourt and severe socio-economic impacts, particularly poverty and depression, which have manifested themselves in crime, as some of the displaced see crime as the only way to survive. Urban regeneration in Port Harcourt must not take the uncivilized burn-and-burn approach, as that will make the intended beneficiaries weep and wail, and shedding tears of so-called unintended consequences that we think are avoidable. The future consequence of this is that if the urban regeneration exercise is not designed holistically by discussing the issues with those likely to be affected before it begins of the demolition, Port Harcourt dwellers will start engaging in riots which may have great consequences if they hear that urban renewal will take place in their communities. Also, it may cause other serious health consequences such as stroke, heart attack, hyper tension and death if approach to urban renewal in Port Harcourt remains stereotyped.

In developing countries, relocation of affected residents and/or payment of compensation commensurate with the value of properties demolished have always been problematic. Relocation is experienced as a challenge particularly for those residents who lived in the urban centre. Since the informal economy is the dominant livelihood source in slum settlements, restoring income sources and social networks after resettlement are crucial. Due to the dynamic idea of casual work, giving open doors particularly to ladies and single-headed families, enabling such families to empower them to participate in elective types of pay age is indispensable for their prosperity. This study uncovers that the beginning stage for the investigation of issues connecting with migration is the acknowledgment of the centrality of home and neighborhood, that is, to the monetary and social prosperity of families.

RECOMMENDATIONS

To guide against socioeconomic implications as found in this research in similar endeavours in the future, the following recommendations are expedient:

➤ The authorities have to make urban renewal very holistic. A holistic urban renewal exercising is the only that counts the price at the citizens of the groups which are in all likelihood to be affected, bring them along, pay vital compensations or relocate them because the case can be earlier than demolition exercising commences at all. If that is done, instances of ill-fitness brought about with the aid of using forceful evictions will now no longer arise.

- To reduce the suffering of urban arms, especially if a place for renovation is marked, reimbursements in the form of "slum Citizens insurance insurances, 'eviction pension' and 'relocation microfinance grants' should be in place. Compensation paid to those who would be affected in any future occurrence of a similar event should commensurate with the value of properties demolished. This is because the study revealed that sometimes compensation received are not anywhere near the value of property demolished, this will help guarantee the social and economic security of slum dwellers during urban renewal exercises.
- With growth in urban population, there is a corresponding need for expansion of the infrastructure such as transportation, water, etc as well as other urban facilities. Indeed, this is tantamount to increasing the pollution capacity of the urban area in order to improve the liveability of the urban.

REFERENCES

- [1]. Abebe, G. 2010. *Resettlement of slum dwellers in contemporary Addis Ababa: The perspectives of relocated households*. Saarbrücken Press.
- [2]. Adekola, P. O. (2016). Migration, urbanisation and environmental problems in Nigeria. In L. Oyefara (Ed.), *Migration and urbanization in contemporary Nigeria: Policy issues and challenges*. UNILAG Press and Bookshop Ltd.
- [3]. Adekola, P. O., Allen, A. A., & Tinuola, R. F. (2017). Socio-economic and health implications of urban renewal on internally displaced persons in Ogun state, Southwestern Nigeria. *Journal of Internal Displacement*,7(1), 13–26.
- [4]. Adekola, P. O., Azuh, D., Adeloje, D. & Amoo, E. (2018). *Urban renewal in Nigeria: a slash and burn approach?*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10668-018-0130-2>
- [5]. Adoga, B. (2016). *Again mass demolition looms in Abuja*. In *The authority online newspaper*. Retrieved January 26, 2016 from www.autho.rityn.gr.com/2016/01/again-mass-demolition-loom-in-Abuja/.
- [6]. Aluko, B. T., & Amidu, A. (2006). *Urban low-income settlements, land deregulation and sustainable development in Nigeria*. In Paper presented at the 5th FIG regional conference, promoting land administration and good governance, Accra, Ghana, March 8–11.
- [7]. Australian Government Department of Foreign Affairs and Trade (2014). *Displacement and resettlement of people in development activities*, Australia.
- [8]. Bronfenbrenner, U. (1992). *Ecological systems theory*. In R. Vasra (Ed.), *Six theories of child development: revised formulations and current issues* (pp. 187-249). Jessica Kingsley publishers.
- [9]. Cernea, M (2000). *Displacement risks in Africa, Refuges, Re-settlers and their host population*.
- [10]. Cernea, M. (2004). *Impoverishment risks, risk management, and reconstruction: A model of*

- population displacement and resettlement*. Paper presented to the UN symposium of Hydropower and Sustainable Development, Beijing October 27-29.
- [11]. Dimuna, K. O. & Omatson, M.E.O. (2010). Regeneration in the Nigerian urban built environment. *Journal of Human Ecology*, 29(2), 141-149.
- [12]. Fadare, W. & Oduwaye, L. (2009). Rebranding Lagos through regeneration. Real CORP 2009 Proceedings Tagungsband, 22-25 April. www.corp.com
- [13]. FDRE (2007). *Plan for urban development and urban good governance*. Ministry of Works and Urban Development, Addis Ababa.
- [14]. George, C. K. (2006). *Basic principles and methods of urban and regional planning*. Libro-Gem Books.
- [15]. Hamnett, C. (1984). Gentrification and residential location theory: A review an assessment. In D. Herbert & R. Johnston (eds.), *Geography and the urban environment: Progress in Research and applications*. Wiley Press.
- [16]. Huang, Y. (2008). Discussion on the protection and utilization of historical heritage, *Shanxi Architecture*, 34(9), 3-10.
- [17]. Jimoh, H. O., Omole, F. K., & Omosulu, S. B. (2013). An examination of urban renewal exercise of Badia East of Lagos State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Education and Research*, 1(5), 1–14.
- [18]. Kara, G. (2011). *The examination of the urban renewal projects: A case study of Trabzon, Turkey*. A paper presented at FIG Working Week 2011 Bridging the Gap Between Cultures, held in Marrakech, Morocco, 18-22 May.
- [19]. Kehinde, S. O. (2003). *Maroko: The agonies of displacement*. Rebonik Publications Limited.
- [20]. Lee, K. L. G. (2008). *Sustainable urban renewal model for a high density Urban-Hong Kong*. In An unpublished PhD Thesis submitted to the Department of Building and Real Estate. The Hong Kong Polytechnic University, Hong Kong, China.
- [21]. McDonald, S., Malys, N. & Meliene, V. (2009). Urban regeneration for sustainable communities. *Baltic Journal of Sustainability*, 15(1), 49-59.
- [22]. Norwegian Refugee Council (NRC). (2015). *Urban displacements*. <http://www.nrc.no/?aid=9188162#.VikPwVJIyNI>
- [23]. Nwanna, C. R. (2012). Gentrification in Lagos State: Challenges and prospects. *British Journal of Arts and Social Sciences*, 5(2), 163–176.
- [24]. Odinaka, S. (2016). *Goods worth millions destroyed as Lagos State Government demolishes Oshodi Market*. Retrieved January 6, 2016 from <http://www.tori.ng/php?77>.
- [25]. Okeke, D. C. (2004). *Environmental and urban renewal strategies: Theoretical and analytical Framework*. Institute of Development Studies.
- [26]. Pankhurst, A. & Piguat, A (2009). *Moving people in Ethiopia: Development, displacement and the state*. Woodbridge.
- [27]. PLB. (2000). *Planning and Lands Bureau's response to public comments in Hong Kong*. Hong Kong SAR.
- [28]. Population Reference Bureau (PRB). (2015). *2014 World population data sheet*. Washington DC: PRB
- [29]. Robinson, W. C. (2003). *Risks and rights: The causes, consequences, and challenges of development-induced displacement*. SAIS-Brookings Institution
- [30]. Rui, L. (2003). *Urban renewal at neighborhood level: A case study of Huangjiadun Neighborhood in Wuhan Urban*.
- [31]. Smith, N. (1979). Toward a theory of gentrification: A back to the urban movement by capital not people. *American Planning Association Journal*, 46(3), 538-548
- [32]. The Social and Economic Rights Action Center (SERAC), Lagos. (2009). *The presidential committee on internally displaced persons*. <http://www.serac@likserve.com.ng>.
- [33]. Uwadiogwu, B. O. (2015). Urban renewal and security issues. *British Journal of Environmental Science*, 3(2), 21–32.
- [34]. Van der Brugge, R. & De Graaf, R. (2010). *Linking water policy innovation and urban renewal: The case of Rotterdam, The Netherlands*. IWA Publishing.
- [35]. Wosu, E & Anele, K (2010). Rural-urban migration of young person from selected conflict ridden communities in Rivers State. A sociological approach. www.academicjournals.org/ajpsir.
- [36]. Zielenbach, S. & Levin, G. M. (2000). *The art of revitalization: Improving conditions in distressed inner-urban neighborhoods*. Garland.